

Joint Technical Symposium (JTS)

PRESERVE THE LEGACY | CELEBRATE THE FUTURE

HILVERSUM, 3-5 OCTOBER 2019

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JTS2019 COLLABORATIVE NOTES

taken by Erwin Verbruggen, Joshua Ng, Rasa Bočytė, and Ross Garrett.

JTS2019 was organized on behalf of the Coordinating Council of Audiovisual Archiving Associations (CAAAA) by AMIA, FIAF, FIAT/IFTA, and IASA. JTS2019 was held in conjunction with the International Association of Sound and Audiovisual Archives (IASA) 50th Anniversary conference and hosted by the Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision.

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About JTS

The Joint Technical Symposium (JTS) is the international scientific and technical event hosted by the audiovisual archives associations that make up the CCAAA. Held every few years, this joint event brings together technical experts from around the world to share information and research about the preservation of original image and sound materials. The 2019 JTS was organized by AMIA, FIAF, FIAT/IFTA, and IASA on behalf of the CCAAA

JTS 2019 was held October 3-5, 2019 in conjunction with the International Association of Sound and Audiovisual Archives (IASA) conference and hosted by the Netherlands Institute for Sound and Vision in Hilversum, the Netherlands.

About CCAAA

The professional archivists that the CCAAA ultimately represents work in institutions such as archives, libraries and museums at national and local level, university teaching and research departments, and broadcast and production organisations.

jts2019.com

<https://www.ccaaa.org/pages/news-and-activities/joint-technical-symposium.html>

JTS2019 DOCUMENTATION

JTS2019 Twitter archive as [TAGSExplorer](#) or [TAGS Archive](#)
JTS2019 images on IASA's [Flickr](#)
Selected conference recordings on Sound and Vision's [Vimeo](#)
Slide decks on [OSF Meetings](#)

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FRIDAY OCT 4 - Theme: REFORMATTING AND RESTORING

WELCOME AND INTRODUCTIONS

Rachael Stoeltje

JTS today & tomorrow: Expand the IASA50 topics & focusing on technical aspects of the field
This edition is the tenth JTS! Combined fields ever more overlapping. Since 1983 hosted every 3 - 5 years. Constant: newest & best ways to reformat analog AV media. What's the next exciting thing on the horizon? Pesky film to new tech - nitrate to acetate, acetate to 2" Quad videotape - ... JTS unveiled new tech. Now developments in what we can do with digitized media. What do our most innovative / creative colleagues do? Our jobs have changed - role of digitization in our lives is significant. No longer "if" digitize, but how & at what scale. JTS is at its core focused - consistently looking at future. Advancements just over the horizon. Therefore most exciting. Prospect of AI in our work - esp. In labour-intensive activities. Sometimes scary horizon. For our purposes hopefully AI can be implemented positively. Developments unveiled today & future. Remember primary purpose - bring together members of the various prof organisations isolated yet working on similar developments. Walls have been disappearing as we face similar dilemmas. Relying on IASA standards - TC01 - 06, FADGI, and similar standards & achievements. SHaring & working together is core goal of CCAA & JTS. Collectively preserving the world's AV heritage & vast sea of 1s and 0s. This year jointly / in tandem with IASA50 📦 & honouring Dietrich Schüller 🇳🇱. Handed out JTS Founder Award, tomorrow 1st JTS Technical Awards.

Eppo van Nispen tot Sevenaer

24/7 technical service. Servicing 17 million Dutch audience. Archivists at the core. Break boundaries everywhere. Preserve the Legacy, Celebrate the Future. We celebrated! Star Trek Tricorder - now online for 60 bucks. Abundance of archives - full of analog data. Once digitized can connect to people. Be on Snapchat cause that's where the next gen of users is. Ridiculous format but 3.5 messages / day, exchanged 1 trillion messages so far. Gone after a day. Heritage for 24 hours. Pieter Abeel at Marvel Nano. Not doomy about AI. Read SuperIntelligence (Nick Boston). It's the way ahead. Google has a greeter. Uses actual human being to connect. Negroponte: Change from atoms to bits is unstoppable. Collection is not in our buildings. Just stuff. Your collection is this age's people - 24 - 35. What makes us happy? Oxytocin. Mix it up: connection. Celebrate the future? Join them. Work on the future of what archives can be, do and must connect. Colourful world of combinations. All of our tasks: how do we get these archives outside and give them back to the people. Wish you all the best! Live long and prosper.

KEYNOTE - Dr. Martha Larson - What can the Archive do for AI... and what can AI do for the Archive

 Recording available at

<https://vimeo.com/showcase/6574370/video/372851500>

<http://places2.csail.mit.edu/demo.html>

Analyze news, analyze videos to predict speech aspects.

Prof. at Radboud and the Delft University of Technology. Developing a new course: AI and the Archive. Studying AI for the past 20 years. How can archives continue to realize AI's full potential? Develops algorithms for multimedia analysis - objective to create human-like annotations by means of training & testing the systems. Deep learning - type of machine learning: cs231n.github.io/convolutional-networks. Input - output. Deep architecture b/c neural network can consist of a lot of layers. Every layer does another transformation of the image. Not only smaller at each layer, also each layer adds to the abstraction of the image. Places demo places2.csail.mit.edu/demo.html. System trained to recognize places - can predict Sound and Vision group pic is a mezzanine. Pretty incredible. Trained on a very large number of examples - human-like way of analysing the scene in the demo. Pic taken at [Multimedia Evaluation Workshop](#) 2016 - yearly meeting prof. Larson chairs where people meet to formulate new tasks. Groups worked on:

- [Flood severity estimation](#) - images gathered from social media & news coverage
- [Eyes and Ears Together](#) - Understand combination of audio & visual based on how-to videos: understand what the object is that is being spoken about with NLP

Serious issues with AI

could be addressed by working more with archives.

- 1995 Informedia (Hauptmann, Smith) - signal-to-noise ratio to split video in speech segments & try to transcribe, add keywords, segment scenes with scene analysis
- 2002 prof. Larson at Fraunhofer - working on similar system - iFinder working on news: speech segments, speaker IDs - system offered as toolkit allowed searching in large collections. Basis for elections coverage in 2009.

2009: very rosy everyone excited about scene segmentation, ... to make archives accessible & searchable.

Thundercloud crept in:

- 2008 Data issues Google audio indexing transcribed Barack as broccoli: not enough names passed on to the system
- 2014 Annotation issues - dresses conflated with robes, kaftans, ... all in one category. Computer vision good in light/dark patterns to recognize people's legs - no such patterns. Annotators apparently tweak. Lost the connection to reality - what's important for an archivist.
- 2016 Data & Annotation - [ImageNet](#) = 14 million photos annotated with ca. 200.000 categories - largest collection used to train systems, widely used. 2019 [ImageNet Roulette](#) scandal: can search what system says about you when uploading photo. Huge problem in 2019: we don't know what's in that corpus, what's in those annotations.

Computer vision / analysis people: it's too much, can't be held responsible for those data! This is where archives come in: they would not say they have no responsibility. You would know what's in your collection. You know how to tell us how to curate that set to prevent mislabeling.

- Patriotridersofamerica image - annotated as flagpole / flagstaff - but there's a lot more going in on that image of bikers holding flags probably during a funeral of a veteran. Compared to system not recognizing an **actual** flagstaff with no flag on it.

PlacesDemo about flooding - did good on mezzanine, but flooding image scene category attributes "slum" and "moist" for a flooded town.

Real problem with large corpora - can't just be applied to real-world problems without careful consideration. Need real-world data that is well-matched to the domain of application. Need Archival experience so we don't train systems that are completely inappropriate for the tasks we need them to do.

- Lack of oversight of data
- Lack of control of annotations
- AI makes bad assumptions about the goal of the tech
- And about the scale at which the problem needs to be solved

Projects: what did the team learn from the archive doing projects with Archives?

- 2005 AudioMining at Fraunhofer with WDR and DW broadcasters - search interface for digi radio collection - search terms for metadata and for audio transcripts. Ugly UI but we were mainly interested in underlying tech. Speaker indication - but "broccoli problem" - not always returning Johannes Rau and missing him. Archivist: we don't see timecodes, we see a pattern - can see it's a two-person interview, which radio program it was. Can

scan and tell if radio program has been mis-cataloged by the speaker pattern - CS people: that's just speaker segmentation, it's easy! Don't push for the techy hard stuff. Machines don't do all the work - experience of archivists does. Lesson: go from wrong goal (look for keywords) to the right (verify cataloging)

- 2001 Speech recognizer - conventional vs unconventional Automated Speech Recognition (ASR) system (for sentence with lots of public transport acronyms): shouldn't output transcript that looks like language but that looks like how it sounds. Need to suspend belief - word-based transcript does better job if our goal is to locate occurrences of keywords in spoken audio.
- 2014 SocialZap application: pulls in tweets allowing text analysis. Really good at recognizing some things: training to recognize not just guitar but girl + guitar. But there were so many things happening during the event. We couldn't find enough data to train the AI to recognise them all. Not mentioned on social media. How to move from general web data to more specific data that allows going deeper?
- 2012-2016 [Video hyperlinking](#) - native idea from here at sound and vision: WWW pages are hyperlinked, why not connect up video connections in that way?
 - AXES project, Mediaeval 2012-2014, TRECVID 2015-2016.
 - Visual & spoken video interaction.
 - Multimodality from the perspective of the person making the video - what is intent, can people see it?
 - Ref. <https://research.utwente.nl/en/publications/multimodal-video-to-video-linking-tuning-to-the-crowd-for-insigh>
 - Missed the amount of time needed to dedicate to scoping this problem
 - Is search & hyperlinking viral? Not competing with Google - driving search with ads, not what we do with archives - aim to freely explore not steer towards being super lucrative.
 - Correct scale: Takes longer & success is more modest than you think
- Now: multimodality of video & sign language - *Jeugdjournaal* with visual translator - used for better annotations for video

What next?

Deep learning - much hype. Still much potential but proceed with caution. AI researchers:

- Need more self-awareness - Lanier "You are not a gadget" Technologists wish every program behaved ... will avoid thinking about computers realistically." Forget often that tech doesn't do what helps users most.
- Need more courage - not being afraid to ask questions: can't say for sure when something's a fire truck, ladder truck, fire engine... archives have humility to think about what the right category is - not trivial: think about what your taxonomy is, lexicon is, how you define things

Archives need AI to support them in their mission

AI needs archive to impose better standards, develop the right goals, target the right scale - and NOW is the moment to act to do course correction for AI!

Thank you to paper authors! The archive must tell AI what is important.

Q&A

- (Brecht) Q: Is the collaboration between media archives and the developers of algorithms crucial to avoid biases?
 - A: Archives serve the public equally, not drive people into a highly individualized worlds like algorithms will (if improperly designed). For an example of the role that public broadcasters are playing within the wide mission of providing an example of AI done right, see the Chris Berry keynote <https://youtu.be/Tr0EclsGTAY> public broadcasters recommendation systems for social cohesions, examples of technology that bring people together rather than split them apart.
 - (David Walsh) Q: technicians used to manually label shots, now AI is doing the job. AI is currently not able to perform that job to the same level of detail. Is it going to catch up soon?
 - A: That's exactly why we need the archive to tell AI: what are the types of annotations that are actually useful to use in the archive.
 - (Howard Besser, NYU) Q: You train the system on material from the past but you expect it to work on material in the future. Most AV material in collections document white men - an obvious bias that influences the algorithms and raises ethical concerns.
 - A: AI assumes that future is a copy of the past. Solutions: 1) Our systems need to reveal their limitations, interfaces should project that (make limitations obvious). 2) Systems that can be easily trained for a specialized purpose using a small amount of well-understood data from the correct domain. Such systems are trained directly before use, and then "thrown out". 3) Need regulations for AI, an infrastructure that help us make a "healthy AI", use it in a responsible way. Don't underestimate the amount of time this will take or the amount of money it will cost. It is a worthwhile investment.
-

Moderated by: Nadja Wallaszkovits

Nick Bergh - A Methodology for Digitizing Wax Cylinders

 Recording available at

<https://vimeo.com/showcase/6574370/video/372851898>

Nadja: "The fascinating details behind his sophisticated method to transfer wax cylinders."

Nick: usually film sound. Started cylinder experiments for early recordings in 2001. Stylus vs optical pickup of grooved media is the eternal debate. Generally - for non-audio engineers:

- styli touching media can seem crude. With picture you can sample what we see (optical film sound). With sound it's very sensitive to variations. Lot of dynamic range. What's possible in pictures isn't in sound - need stable speed.
- Optical is limited in resolution - 8-bit or less compared to 22-bit possible in analogue capture and risky for artefacts: jitter. There's no raw. Often not realtime so harder to make adjustments. But it's important for broken discs, missing info from analog sources. Still important to have good analogue transport. Critical to use highest-quality material.

Current machine - 5 of which in use- combine both methods.

- 2001 cylinder machine - aimed to have same playback but cylinders wobble (b/c small diameter)
- 2015 "race car" cylinder machine with laser to track the eccentricity and compensate for it in real time ("DeWobble")
- Stereo RIAA cylinder with moving-coil cartridge - good to know where the limits of the technology are - little extreme as an approach, tried getting it in smaller package
- Current laser helps (1) center (2) outputs 48 kHz tone to demodulate (3) tracks optical playback to know where groove's center is (micron accurate)

What to do with cracks & missing sections? Optical's great for that & for initial discovery, for tuning transfer before using the stylus and for sections where you don't want to hurt your stylus

- Confocal probe attached to Endpoint machine
- Laser used for centering is also good for extracting sound - can be tilted & made sensitive to groove velocity rather than just distance
- When moved down can be angled on the cylinder
- Tracking accomplished with little 4K camera
- Software gives recommendation for playback stylus based on material type

Obstacle course records in Hi-Fi era - broken cylinder recording for comparison.

Same approach (combined) can be used for damaged lacquer discs!

Q&A

- Nadja: "Everybody's dreaming of your machine"
- Have this machine in Prague since July - very happy to show it with Scottish sound engineer Tony Allen, collaborate, thanks for this opportunity!
- George: Could you speak to anti-wow post-processing?

- Typically really helpful for blue amberalls & things - hard to get squared up on the mandrill
 - Langusa: Is this machine available commercially?
 - 5 in use already and going strong
 - How do you control the horizontal movement in optical mode?
 - Camera attached to the laser does FFT at the grooves, laser knows where the bottom of the groove is - will assume where the bottom of the groove is, can move around inside of the groove
 - Gisa: Can you apply this to cylinder negatives as well?
 - Possibly, I guess? Sensors have to get real small (fibre-optics?) but would take a bit of engineering
-

George Blood - Have You Ever Tried...?

An exploration of myth, queries, and neat things to try in audiovisual preservation.

 Recording available at

<https://vimeo.com/showcase/6574370/video/372849884>

Nadja: The "grand seigneur", most experience with transfer!

George: QA processes: Digitization is a system - each component's behaviour and its interaction may yield different results. All testing done when time was available, input welcome.

Quick Premiere video display reading lesson - waveform monitor

What impact does routine cleaning have on video playback?

- With audio you clean the heads and transport, with video you clean the tapes before playing
- Betacam, brushes in the video head. Thing that breaks the most often. But maybe no need to clean as often? U-matic, maybe cleaning by default.
- Findings are inconclusive: range of things happens, not sure whether changes due to cleaning of something else. Also samples quite small.
- Conclusion: clean, especially if it's been baked. No proof that it does harm.

Can you clean a videotape too many times?

- Use QCTools to compare passes - random errors come and go
- Benefits only found in the first two cleaning passes
- No RF reduction between the first and 100 passes
- Examine tape for existing damage & continue to clean videotape for routine digitization

D2 Playback - native analog or transcoded digital?

D2 is composite digital bitstream format (no longer supported)

Staying in the digital domain is clearly superior over composite - but very rare to find one of these boxes ("rarer than a hen's teeth"!)

Effects of aging on multi-band complimentary noise-reduction software

- Errors will be large, variable and impossible to get out.
- Dolby 363 (Dolby A) - good quality
- DBX180 (Type 1) - introduces noise in harmonics b/c of bad design but easy to fix (move to external power supply) - signal is fine until it gets to the output
- Systems work properly after 30 years (Dolby build quality is better)
- Testing not complicated

Drilling through mu-metal head blocks to access azimuth screw - bad idea?

- Azimuth adjustment availability varies with different models
- Mu-metal has magnetic projection properties

- Dynamics are the same pre- and post-drilling - so yes: it is possible to do this and retain the shielding properties (don't DIY though - stress can damage mu-metal properties)

Should we trust alignment tapes?

- Alignment tapes seems to give weird results

- Compare aging and new tapes. D is the weird drop off

- Already talking to vendors.

- Learn what correct is and be ready to investigate

6. We trust alignment tapes. Should we?

- **Conclusions:**
 - A little skepticism is healthy = sometimes something IS wrong
 - Trust your vendors to do the right thing – nobody supports analog for the money these days
- **What should you do?**
 - Don't be afraid to investigate; and ask questions
 - Learn what correct is, and be ready to investigate

Is it ok to play audio tapes backwards?

- When you turn tape over, you change two variables
- More variability for frequency response for playback than for playing backwards
- Lower frequency distortion is lower in reverse
- Phase response varies widely between machines - but is it audible?

How long does a diamond stylus last?

- Supplier: 150 plays
- Project: every 10 days
- Marcos Sueros at IASA 2017
- Dust & debris, tar build up - comes off in ultrasonic cleaner - long before wear
- Corrosion persists - but impact unclear
- Human element: bents, damaged assemblies visible before wear
- Clean & check your styli often, replace at first sign of damage

Is every scan of the same film on the same scanner the same?

- Charts jump around - decrease in dynamic range b/c of leaving the scanner on
- Images visibly different on each scan.
- Need more test to know what's going on

Oliver Danner - How to Achieve Authentic Results With Modern Soundtrack Scanners

Slides available at	https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/ETZGA
Recording available at	https://vimeo.com/showcase/6574370/video/372852041

- Transfer of optical film - hard to achieve authentic results

Authenticity

- Some say film can never be authentic, real, or original

Modern soundtrack scanners

- JTS2010, JTS2016 all mention COSPP Xi2K (Development started in 1985, does Chase still exist? Website disappeared from Deluxe site), Sound Direct (since 2004, Danish developer still there) & Resonances (available since 2012, originally Sondor, now taken over by DFT)
- All proprietary systems - problematic for authenticity of output as we don't know what the systems do in detail
- Software products: AEO-Light (open source, since 2011), Image to Sound Tools (since 2015, integral part of Arriscan XT, developer is here at JTS!), OSires (since 2016 project planned by Andreas Kahlo for open source soundtrack extraction software, now employed at Cube-Tec, so who knows?)
- More modern scanners: projectors! Using Dolby off-the-shelf components. No software of microprocessors involved but can't contain spread. Narrow slit height.
- Slit height varies across time and space
- Why slit height affects nonlinear distortion (noise level)? Grain structure causes noise introduction - narrower slit (as standardised from 1981) projected much more detail into the audio signal - reduced scanning area leads to noise increase - historic books have pages and pages of calculations on this
- Red light reverse readers is typically stereo - which leads to half a dB less noise
- Uneven illumination of the scanning area

Sliphardt parameter

- Do we *really* want to trade in an authentic listening experience for an unprecedented high-frequency response (read: extra noise)?
- E-mail: o.danner@gmx.de

Q&A

- Nick: big productions often do cost cutting but sound quality is important - we always do sound positives - golden age of Hollywood's sound engineering was incredible - many papers written from '30s - to '50s, lots of details on optimizing slit height. Made the choice not to make it as narrow even though they had the capabilities.
 - Oliver: Just wanted to show that getting a modern soundtrack scanner doesn't mean you will be getting the same results as an analogue scanner.

- Dietrich: question is simple & complicated at the same time b/c film is considered to be a piece of art - any improvement beyond reproduction fidelity of the time is seen as a malversation of the original. In audio we don't have that problem (only in a minute way) b/c nobody thinks the authentic listening experience at the time is a worthwhile experience! Our question needs to be: what do we want to preserve - the document on the carrier or what was perceived at the time?
 - And it's always a compromise
 - Michael: we should not go back to the deficient sound quality of earlier days for *any* sound recording method. There's no reason to degrade. Michael hates the academy recording curve.
 - Nick: these were top engineers at the time who made decisions of what was right. Academic curve was definitely too steep - a lot of SMPTE papers talk about this compromise. Studio reproducers wanted best quality. Theatre reproducers were hoping for rolloff.
 - George: Producers mix through with the knowledge of the curves
 - Nick: optical sound different from tape - even if you capture after 20kHz not usable in the same way
-

Moderated by: Erwin Verbruggen

**Marjolein Steeman & Tristan Zondag -
MXF Repair Flow
*How to Plan a Major Asset Migration***

Slides available at	https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/8HBMS
Recording available at	https://vimeo.com/showcase/6574370/video/372851196

- 60% of MXF files passed
- approximately 22% returned with errors
- QC tested with Baton?
- Rewrapped files 220019
- Transcoded 16323

Q&A

- Q (Stephen, BFI): BPMN Business Process Management N(?). Do you use it to trigger scripts?
 - A: Only use it to visualise.
- Q(Silvester): What caused most errors?
 - A: Largest percentage of errors are the older files. In the beginning, standards are maturing. Files delivered today, 99% okay. Vendor does QC before sending to us.
- Q(Andy Martin, DAMsmart): Validation, does it on the spot or???
 - A: QC goes through the same profile, either green or red.
- Erwin: Have you looked at others for examples of how to tackle such a project?
 - Tristan: We're the first to do this. Mass repair of MXF. Presented at FRAME, no one else seemed to be doing it.
 - Brecht: ORF, Austria, have done a massive repair of files.

James Lindner - Using Computer Vision Technology to Accurately and Objectively Determine Motion Picture Film Condition

Slides available at	https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/7DKQE
Recording available at	https://vimeo.com/showcase/6574370/video/372850485

FILMIC, research project. To rethink digital preservation for film. Build an extensible model. Designed to be collaborative.

Today, research project turning into a product. Something you can buy.

How can we best preserve FILMIC content?

More and more uses for film as time goes by.

- New tools for digital film preservation

Cinequal:

- Rapid iteration. Since Jan 2019, 3 prototypes.
- Prototyped using 3D printing - Ultimaker
- Scout 16i

- No tension rod. Motor control friction.

How can we objectively determine film condition and use that info to manage a collection?

By measuring things, we can know what is right what is wrong. Lessons from the semiconductor industry.

Utilising SMPTE standards to benchmark expected dimensions “The Golden Frame” for film condition.

Damage detection, using machine vision scanning, similar to production line scanning. Used to have resolution problems in the past. Now no longer.

The goal is not to replace the film inspector but to enable them to do their job better. Proved to be 93% accurate for finding issues when tested.

Metadata provides a carrier up to a feature level data on the issues and a color code for overall condition.

Poster Presentations / Poster Sessions

Preserving Culturally and Historically Important Collections via Community Archiving Workshop (CAW) (Sub: The CAW: Manila AsiaVisions AV Collection Project) by Rosemarie Roque

 Slides available at:

<https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/84EBT>

The J.H. Kwabena Nketia Archives: African Archives Best Practices -- A Case Study for In-House Digitization in the Developing World by Nathaniel Kpogo Worlanyo and Audra V. Adomenas

 Slides available at:

<https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/24YRP>

Balancing Open Access & Intellectual Property Rights at the National Cultural Audiovisual Archives of India by Irfan Zuberi

 Slides available at:

<https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/MXS5V>

Moderated by: Kate Murray

**Jörg Houpert & Lars Gaustad -
Q&A on Conservation and Restoration Ethics in Digital Times
*Refining Ethical Requirements and Ease their Communication by Introducing
Visual- and Mathematical Models***

- IASA TC-03: no TC-03 currently has diagrams - should change for communicating better
 - This week summary published - training course: 7 commandments for AV preservation
 - Don'ts: lossless compression, of course!
 - Original version of TC-03 was a two-pager, now back to that origin
 - It's only 20 (dense) pages, there's a need for addressing people on different channels
 - Transforming textual descriptions into visual models... (abstract)
 - IASA TC-03 now 4th edition (2017), French translation, Spanish, German, Italian, Russian, Swedish (all 2005), Czech, Portuguese (2017), Chinese - now the simplified Technical Version - working title "do not delete valuable data unintended"
 - Stimulate the conversation about the ethical foundation for both new generations and engineers
 - Ethical requirements for engineers - at some point in time AV media is digitized and brought into a MAM. Then it's data. What are compliance rules?
 - Technicians ask for compliance rules
 - Migration tools - where can engineers can get proper background info?
 - Goal: turn TC-03 into attractive literature for millennials
 - Natural language is not easy. Controlled languages don't sound natural.
 - Simple binary operations
 - Different modelling languages (BPMN, UML)
 - Example - TC-03 text translated for techies
 - Technical people like short, clear rules
 - Ethical rules become sexy
 - Conservation not as easy as the restoration parts
-

Jean-Hugues Chenot -

Saphir: Digitizing broken and cracked or delaminated lacquer 78 rpm records using a desktop optical scanner

Special focus on cracked lacquer discs

- Louis Laborelli & ... other inventor
- Wall of disc grooves indicate signal - left and right signal, in mono both say the same thing
- Buchman Meyer's 1930 method for measuring the amplitude the width of the modulated signal by ruler - measuring the reflection signal
- Rheinberg illumination
- Compact optical scanning head casts white light - lighting at 45 degrees to see groove wall, in rare cases horizontally
- Earlier mechanical setup allowed for ~3 records / day
- New scanner (Dec 2018) has nearly 50 flashes / second - standard disc scanned in 30 mins
- Cracked lacquer discs (10 - 20k of them in Ina alone) - delaminating
 - Cracked discs covered under glass plate
- Sound examples!
- System can go up to 22 kHz for 78 rpm, up to 12-15 kHz for 33 rpm
- Bill of materials is less than 5.000 euro - trying to open source the software

Peter Schallauer - Quality Control Experiences and Effectiveness in a Large-Scale Film Digitization Project

Recording available at

<https://vimeo.com/showcase/6574370/video/372852212>

- Automated QC at Indiana University with [VidiCert](#)
- PDF reports of framing errors, image loss, faded stock, unsteadiness, ...

- QC statistics on the project Dec 2017 - Aug 2019 - 12.000 titles, 24.000 files

Conclusions

- Approach to QC is a project strength
 - Allows IU to better understand its diverse collections and adapt workflows
 - Enables high quality archive package
- Submission Package QC
 - Ensures packages meets archiving standards
- VidiCert Image and Sound QC
 - Integrates very well with IU workflow and Submission Package QC
 - Image and audio issues can be detected quickly
 - Detailed automatic and interactive detection functions helps in finding the origin of an issue
 - QC + Re-Scan reduces the total defects rate by more than a factor of 5
- Strengthens IU's relationship with the service provider
- Very beneficial cooperation between IU and JR

SATURDAY OCT 5 - Theme: BIG COLLECTIONS, BIG ASSETS, BIG DATA

Moderated by: Rachael Stoeltje

Giorgio Trumpy - Historical Film Colors and Digital Cinema

Slides available at	https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/SKGWR
Recording available at	https://vimeo.com/showcase/6574370/video/372852649

Building a versatile film scanner that is capable of capturing historical film colours. Digitising a film - a sort of time travel, need to ask ourselves what the original audiences were seeing. Capture of colour digitally comes with limitations, does not provide an accurate result straight away. Limited to RGB spectrum to recreate colours. To reproduce the original colour digitally, need to perform colour grading and compare it with the original projection but often the original is damaged and cannot be used for comparison anymore. To get away from the RGB spectrum limitations, they built a multi-spectrum filter that illuminates the negative.

Jörg Houpert - Requirements and New Technologies for the Inspection of Photochemical Film

How to make a good decision on the future of your collection without knowing it well? Diagnosis of the current condition is essential. Manual inspection process that is becoming more and more difficult to perform with the obsolescence of equipment and the lack of expertise:

- Physical condition
- Photographical state (densities in different parts, resolution, etc.)
- Content and provenance
- Check the audio track

Film scanning is not lossless - reformatting needs to be documented in detail. The characteristics of the film scanner add to the characteristics of the scanned film material, together they form the characteristics of the digital surrogate.

QUADRIGA CALIBRATION INSPECTOR:

- Software that analyses the film scanner characteristics - optical path, film transport, coding and processing
- Produces a report that describes the characteristics of the scanner so it could be referenced in the future.

How does it support the inspection process:

- Improved preparation of materials for digitisation
- Selection of the best copy for the digitisation
- Guarantees that the digitalisation does not do any damage to the film

QUADRIGA INSPECTOR SCAN REPORT

- Provides extensive details on the condition of the film
- Descriptive and technical metadata, possible to include images of the physical reel
- Splices, density, shrinkage
- XML, interactive html and PDF

**Thierry Delannoy and Benjamin Alimi -
HDR, 4K UHD : What Future for Archives ?**

The Archives and the New Color Spaces, Are They Friends or Enemies?

- Using HDR while respecting the film tones of classic films.
- SDR - HDR: majority of TVs sold nowadays are HDR-enabled.

Figure: 2K, 4K, 8K

- HDR more realistic - but what with fiction?
 - “Viewer would have to wear sunglasses when it’s a bright scene”
 - Pixels increase - UHD-2 up to 8K pixels (leading to 33 million pixels) (UHD-1 up to 4K)
 - Greater precision - interlaced frames (comes from CRTs) for compatibility with SD
 - New norm exceptes 100 – 120 frames / second
 - More shades of colour - BT.709 seen as too narrow/limited to represent visible colors
 - In real life the shiny information (shines) gives perceived curve of the object - shows the shape
 - [BT.2020](#) - current equipment cannot reproduce - so using P3 colour space as intermediary
 - Broader range of contrasts
 - Indoor / outdoor perception (really dark room with really bright light from window)
 - Increased Luma space gives??
 - Improved reproduction
- Provides signal with all information - all information conserved in low highlights and indications added so TV can do recording according to its abilities
- EU limits power consumption

Various Types of HD/HDR - trade war on specifics 🗡️💣🔫☠️👤

HDR ecosystem September 2018

Figure source: <https://www.linkedin.com/feed/update/urn:li:activity:6447473804741607424>

(hat tip to the amazing projector in Theatre 1!) 👍 😊 🗣️

IMPROVEMENTS

- Resolution
- FramPITFALLSes/second: frames have to be artificially added
- Levels of contrast - 14 stops instead of 8 (BT.709),
 - Kodak announced 14 stops capture for its recent film stock
 - Image: bright parts of pictures better reproduced
- Increased colour space = good news for tinted & toned films that couldn't properly be reproduced in BT.709
- Methodology - provided a film is captured in 16-bit 4K, this tech brings many possibilities for reproduction, in terms of image reproduction but also contrast colours and shades present in the film.
-
- Latitude of errors increases
- BT.2020 adds colours inexistant in photochemical film. Have to be careful, we don't want these values.

Conclusion

- Super realistic images is not the essence of analogue cinema
- HDR can reveal information present in the film negative
- Real film can still compete with digital tools - it's far from obsolete!
- Restore in HDR still with the help of DOP and Director, if they're alive, so that it's closest to the original

Q&A

- Giorgio Trumpy: recently switched to UV version of the horseshoe X-Y chromaticity diagram, imho you should switch to the UV range cause it's more perceptually true
- Andrea Kalas: does HDR give different results scanning 4K or 8K?

- A: Didn't try - 8K for 70 mm
- Andrea: doing a lot of HDR (at Paramount)
- Jörg Houpert: I'd be more positive about the advantage to get the colours right - that's a big step, highlight how positive that is! Every new tech has pro & cons, but choosing well it offers a great deal of opportunities!
 - A: HDR restorations (done well) are a strong trend!

Figure: summary of impact areas of HDR. _____

Moderated by: Erwin Verbruggen

Pelle Snickars, Filip Allberg, Johan Oomen - Video Reuse Detector

 Recording available at <https://vimeo.com/showcase/6574370/video/372853376>

Pelle Snickars:

Video reuse detector <https://www.cadeah.eu/> (spin off of [EUscreen](#))

European History Reloaded = Research + Tech.

Trying to see what happens to archival footage when it's out on the web.

- What new perspectives do digital curations bring?
- How can audiovisual archives better foster the re-use of Europe's audiovisual heritage?

Vaporware = microgenre of electronic music, film, internet memes, since 2010. Reuse footage from the former Soviet Union. Different stories. Examples:

- https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=bn2YF_gvCfE
- <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=dun7Ra1sLJM>

Johan Oomen:

Examples of video fingerprinting from the Fraunhofer IDMT institute. TV news from 3pm, 5pm, 8pm. Large portions of footage are reused continuously throughout the day.

Example of audio fingerprinting. Color coding means similarity. Which segments have been reused at which time. 24 hours radio streams.

Example of Video hyperlinking. Documentary of years after 2nd World War. It has a lot of archival footage. Interface allows you to switch from linear broadcast to its underlying clips. Was done manually. <http://www.nadebevrijding.nl/watch/episode1>

Filip Allberg:

Similarities of videos.. It depends.

Intentional attacks to overcome copyright infringement tech

- Flipping
- Camcording
- Picture-in-picture

We want to be able to manage all of these in our tool:

- Center of the frame if point of interest.
- Features like faces should still be the same
- Flip and overlay it on itself, can handle the distortion
- Color. Say if a tint is added. Look at RGB-triples, its relation to each other, not its actual value.

- Audio
- Keyframe generation. Ideally 1s
 - Homogenize each segment. Even if it's time-dilated, it'll still be the same.

Cropping

Not always true, but often enough.

Folding

To be robust against flipping

Folding

Questions?

filip.allberg@umu.se

https://github.com/humlab/video_reuse_detector/

Contact: filip.allberg@umu.se

Source code https://github.com/humlab/video_reuse_detector

Lyndon Nixon -

ReTV: Bringing Broadcaster Archives to 21st-century Audiences

How ReTV Solutions Can Optimise Audiovisual Content for Online Publication and Maximise User Engagement

Recording available at <https://vimeo.com/showcase/6574370/video/372853166>

Linear TV viewing going down. Mobile, on-demand going up. Audience fragmented. Broadcasters forced to put content up on YouTube.

(2011 vs 2019) Average daily media consumption on mobile internet increased 504%

Predictive analytics for topic analysis:

- Trending topics analysis
- Collecting documents published online daily
- performing annotation and keyword extraction
- temporal annotation (date extraction)
- Event extraction (online calendars, wikidata)

Content repurposing

- What audiovisual content and in what form can be published?
- Video analysis (scene, shot and sub-shot)
- Labeling visual concepts
- Video length restrictions (need to be optimised for social media) - using neural network for summarisation

Content Recommendation

- When to publish content and on what channel
- Daily video summary delivered on a chatbot
- Recommendation for what content will be trending on future dates
- Finding the most relevant content to consumers, repurposing content that they would not discover otherwise

Bertram Lyons & Dan Fischer - Structural Signatures Using Source-specific Format Structures to Identify the Provenance of Digital Video Files

Slides available at	https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/YSAKX
Recording available at	https://vimeo.com/showcase/6574370/video/372852444

Structures

- By design these structures have information about the Size:TYPE:payload
- All data is contained in boxes, by design boxes can be skipped
- Rules are not generally defined
- This can be customised : define your own boxes
- Internal structures are flexible and variable

- With the ASCII character value, started to see patterns
- Some video files on different devices had different wrappers in place

- How do files of the same wrapper format differ in structure?
- How does it relate to the source?
- So what happens if I make changes?

- 16 structures changed,
- 3 new appeared
- 1 changed its name

- How to compare the changes and identify the trends?
- Method: tools needed to parse files, focusing on structures and not be misled, "If I don't know it. Don't worry about it"
- Generated an XML profile of the data, this is processed into a database to run queries on the information

- Using signatures, followed names, position, field, depth
- Once signatures were developed for files, they could be compared to another signature for a different profile
- 75 samples from 15 different devices were analysed
- Clustering of brand profiles, relationships from different devices matched with similar models

- Added a large data set to AWS. 11,525 sample files 122 brands, 1058 devices, 61 editors (adobe, FCP etc)
- Distinct signatures for different brands
- Editors have a distinct profile to their brand
- So when changing your files in different editors it will definitely change the file significantly
- Proprietary information is often dropped when moving between files and devices

Why does it matter?

- What are the potential losses?
- How can we know what that loss will be and what can we do
- Why re-wrap?
- Or should we keep the files original for the

Moderated by Lars Gaustad

Franz Hoeller - DeepRestore ***AI techniques for Digital Film Restoration***

 Slides available at

<https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/SMRZH>

Vision

- Efficient filters
- Cheaper restoration

Goal

- AI-based method for restoration

Existing AI methods

- Colorization of b&w
- Upscaling
- Inpainting
- Dust & Scratch

Upscaling

- NVIDIA Up-Res vs. DIAMANT Bicubic Filtering
- Scratches sharper, grain structure clumps together, different.
- <insert examples>
- Conclusion
 - Modern images, not too big of a difference than classical methods
 - NVIDIA slightly sharper
 - Classical method gives more predictive results

Inpainting

- NVIDIA AI Playground allows to test <https://www.nvidia.com/research/inpainting/>
- Deep Video Inpainting with AI - does not produce crisp results, blurs the image. But future developments look promising.
- <https://github.com/mcahny/Deep-Video-Inpainting>
- AI for inpainting are often trained on celebrity image datasets that are not suitable for film restoration

DeepDust

- Testset 1 samples from ~300 different movies (SD-4K)
- Testset 2 100 samples from one movie (2K)

- DeepDust Model

More info: <http://www.hs-art.com/index.php>

Li Ang - Bring New Life to Media Assets with Artificial Intelligence

Slides available at

<https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/ZQN2X>

What exactly is AI?

How to label media data for AI to train it?

10 years challenge

James Lindner -

**Moving Image Metadata-based Finding Aids Using Artificial Intelligence
*Northeast Historic Film Will Create an Archival Moving Image Content
Database for AI Research***

 Slides available at

<https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/GT3P9>

Metadata for film language. Not about the individual frames about what the film tells visually. AI as a finding aid for film language elements. We're training AI in a very literal way - asking AI to show us a boat, but the results we get are without much nuance and context, finding depicted objects (labelling objects within then) but not what the viewer perceives of the images.

The shower killing sequence from *Psycho* - AI would tell us that it is about a shower, shower curtain, water, drain, a knife BUT it is not! It would not tell us that it is about a murder. You cannot tell from a single shot that it is about a murder, you need to watch the whole sequence and understand the moving image, film language and editing.

How can we train AI to recognise film language?

- archives need to provide examples of film language - we need to be part of the process
- We need a different kind of AI training - need examples of inference rather rather direct reference

Creating an AI film database for scientists to develop AI - annotating moving image examples with film language to train AI on it. Helping AI understand the language of shots and editing.

<https://www.kaggle.com/c/open-images-2019-object-detection>

<https://www.kaggle.com/criptexcode/mpst-movie-plot-synopses-with-tags>

We need name authorities for film language.

SATURDAY OCT 5 - Theme: STATUS AND IMPACT OF TECHNOLOGY & PROGRAMMES AND SOLUTIONS

Moderated by: Kate Murray

Brian Wheeler - If I Knew Then What I Know Now ***Evolution of MDPI's Post-digitization Processing***

 Slides available at

<https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/WJH4Y>

- MDPI digitization > preservation & access pipeline
 - Physical storage database
 - Avalon for access
 - Memnon for bulk digitization
- All objects stored as BagIt bags on the tape system - which looks like a giant POSIX system
- Software - RedHat linux, cron-driven processing, workflow in Perl (frowned upon but most experience with & libraries to talk, 6 months of coding needed) & copious logging
- Dedicated hardware for transcoding
- 8 scripts run the workflow - most less than 200 lines, libraries do the heavy lifting
- ~100 maintenance / reporting scripts
- Interfacing [HPSS](#) - only run by high-energy labs
 - Tape library
 - Like an ftp client
 - Created a staging service that sorts requests in a way that's acceptable to the system

Q&A

- Stephen: How do you manage knowledge exchange between developers?
 - Fairly good documentation, 1-person task, others know the Perl scripts, conceptually simple enough to keep in 1 person's brain
-

Etienne Marchand - Mass Digitization Systems and Open-source Software *A Viable Combination?*

 Slides available at

<https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/76WU5>

- Started video > file transfers 20 years ago.
- Now at 3d digitization system - hoping it'll work until everything's done
- Collection of 135,000 Betacam SP tapes from legal deposit 1995-2001
- Aimed to digitize 120 tapes / day, using Flexicart (?)
 - Automated dubbing
 - Automated analysis and trimming
 - QC reinforced
 - LTO storage - J2K, ProRes, V210, FFV1
 - Hoped to increase efficiency and make the system scalable
 - Increase flexibility and logging
 - Compatibility with problem tapes, NO TC, damaged CTL track
- Needed to use FFmpeg as an encoding engine
 - Drawbacks from FFmpeg, need expertise, little documentation, software releases need to be qualified
 - FFmpeg must be standalone, some external modifications were made
 - FFmpeg file analysis and automatic trimming
- File Checks:
 - One pass of color bars check type 1
 - One pass of color bars check type 2
 - Black & silence detection
 - Parsing of detection results
 - Trim in and out points, determined by FFmpeg?
- Open-source Software
 - FFmpeg
 - Perl
 - Mediainfo
 - MPV
 - MongoDB

Inhouse - trimming script

- Manual QC

Microservices approach

Need to preserve ffmpeg skills in-house, service providers won't help with it

System cost is 1/3d (!) of previous one

Q&A

- Andrea Kalas: Academy Open source initiative - associated with Linux Open Source Foundation - engineering support for OS projects www.aswf.io
- Stephen McConnachie: please share your examples to [ffmprovizr](https://ffmprovizr.com)

**Anthony Allen & Martin Mejzr - New Phonograph: Enthusiasm and
Inspiration as a Driving Force**
How to Leverage Your Content to Overcome Budgetary Constraints

<no notes taken>

Moderated by: Etienne Marchand

**Karen Cariani & James Pustejovsky -
Automated Creation of Descriptive Metadata for Large Media Archives
*Creating Open Source Tools and Workflows With the Experts***

 Slides available at

<https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/XEUGA>

AAPB

- Material comes from 1000's different sources
- Metadata is varied and inconsistent
- Large variety of content
- Used Kaldi
- Created a crowdsourcing project to increase the iteration
- WGBH
- Used 10 speakers to test the human versus computer detection
- Contact Karen for the links for the tools used
- Crowdsourcing corrections has varied results
- A small amount has been corrected but more an engagement piece

Zooniverse "roll the credits"

3 new games were created

- NYPL - FIXit +
- JSON transcripts are stored in S3
- Later Indexed for keywords in AWS
- Indexed points can be time stamped and linked to transcript /audio
- Kaldi tool is effective for English, but not as good for other languages
- 81% accuracy for english, not including punctuation and grammar
- 80,000 text transcripts have been processed
- 95% accurate for 1069 - english, boston
- \GitHub Kadi WGBH
- Open source and available to use
- The Elasticity of human mind is not there yet fro machines
- Many attributes require different tools to extract the key information
- Re-running the tool and re-education of the machine is needed to make it for effectively
- Looking for data that is verifiable in news collection, like introductions to a guest that can be tied to a facial recognition

James:

- AI+NLP for archives

- Language tools for LAPPS
- CLAMS workflow editor
- The Data goes beyond text, there is TC time specific information, Captions, logos, subtitles etc.
- The language data is more simplified,
- Pipelines to solve language issues
- Used galaxy workflow engine
- LAPPS-Galaxy
- JSON - interop
- Wrapps the text entirely
- Machine learning and pre-filtering so when you arrive at the KADI model there is less to do
- Workflow galaxy engine - WF container - REST API -
- MMIF multimedia interchange format
- Character or time based anchor

1. Load data
2. Wrap in MMIF
3. Parse
4. Visualize (keywords)
5. Filter
6. Slate parsing
7. OCR
8. Get out the metadata?!
9. Credit parsing

- CLAMS.AI
- CHAPTERING
- FULL NER and parsing over transcriptions
- Prototype platform Dec 5 2019

API will allow you to pull out the data set

Adam Tovell and Andy Irving - IIF for AV *Improving Access to Audio Archives*

 Slides available at

<https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/RZG7Q>

IIF for archive

British Library: 1-2M content items

- Save our sounds program was initiated to preserve the collection
- 2017 “unlocking our sound heritage”
- Raise awareness of the heritage of the sound collection
- Working with 10 hub partners across the UK
 - Goal: 160,000 digital items - 1M
 - Partnering with regional depositories
 - Supplying resources
 - Staff
 - Training
 - Digitising and capturing local content
 - Network of institutions to capture
- Content ranges from simple to really complex
- Simple commercial releases,
- Location recordings, different speeds, tape types, directions and locations on any given tape
- This increased the complexity of the metadata
- Tapes can switch direction in the middle and confuse the contents

IIF:

- International image interoperability framework
- *Now the AV!
- Community that develops and shares API's
- Presentation aPI, includes titles label structure etc
- Goal to describe complex AV works in an interoperable way
- Access, annotation
- To present time based media consistently with image based objects
- Physical structure + Logical structure, to aid in arrangement of sections in time
- You can choose or switch between either structure
- Redaction - oral histories where something needs to be removed from audio
- Sections will be inserted with generated silence
- IIF authentication workflow/API

- Can you access it? No, will give the means to remove privs
- Has been rolled out for new music and incoming digital collections I
- IIF is about API's will be available to researchers
- System of interchange for text and annotation

Q; redaction, problems with automating the redaction, how to do this?

A: done via cataloguers at the moment but would look to do this in the future

JSON LD 1.1

Raymond Drewry - What Good is an Ontology Anyway?

Ontology. What makes a thing a thing. How does it relate to other things? Very useful for communication.

- It has a specified domain.
- RDF is the preferred language.
- You can connect systems together.
- But it's just a definition

Problem 1 What things does the ontology cover?

- If it's not in the definition, ontology can't (or at least it shouldn't) be used for it.
- Some are placeholders and implementers can define them as they wish.

Problem 2

Problem 3

- Humans like to use words. Machines have problem with that.
- Cinematographer vs. Director of Photography

What is an identifier?

What makes a good identifier?

- Should link to other identifiers.

Ontology + Identifier = Linked Data

We're a research lab. So we said why not? We built an ontology.

- Treat provenance as an essential item. We want to be able to say who said it, where did we get it from.
- Languages

How we did it?

What can we do?

- Connect 12 different sources

Applications

Ontology	EBU Role Codes	EJAF Glossary 2014	IMDB	BFI	AFI	Wikidata	VIAF 3 letter code	CISAC 2 letter code	TMDB
productionDesigner	5.1	B.6.1	production_designer	Production Designer		P2554		PD	Production Design
artDirector	5.3.1	B.6.2		Art Director	art direction	P3174		PD	Art Direction
setDesigner	5.4.1	B.6.5		Set Designer	set decoration	P4608	std	PD	Set Decoration
dirOfPhotography	6.1, 6.2.1	B.5.1	cinematographer	Director of Photography, Cinemaphotographer	photography	P344	cng	CM	Director of Photography, Cinematography
sfxSupervisor	5.10.2	B.8.1		Special Effects Supervisor	special effects				
composer	17.1.7	B.11.1	composer	Original Music, Music, Composer, Music composed and conducted by	music	P86	cmp	MC	Music, Original Music Composer
director	20.16	B.3.1	director	Directed by, Director	director	P57	drt	RE	Director
producer	20.1	B.2.3	producer	Produced By, Producer	producer	P162	pro	PC	Producer
execProducer	20.2	B.2.4		Executive Producer		P1431			

Genres

- No ontology. Can be anything...

We wanted to see whether there are any consistency across them?

Wikidata is better. Graph not tree. More connections.

Exploring ontology

Find everyone who has been in a movie with Sylvester Stallone, find all their movies and group them by genre

Q&A

- Pedro Felix, Portugal: a few years ago, we built a community ontological tool. Get ppl to describe things. Crowdsourcing. Will share the link.
- Stephen McConnachie, BFI, FIAF Cataloguing Committee: FIAF Cataloguing manual has a PDF glossary. We are trying to make it an ontological, machine readable format.
- Silverster Stöger, NOA: FIAF cataloguing manual, main book on my shelf.
- (?) : important for those doing text based scraping. Need to have something to test against.

SPARQL Tools

- neo4j
 - neptune
 - Graph.js
-

Moderated by: Brecht Declercq

**Eleanore Alquier and Gautier Poupeau -
Evolution of Data Management for New Uses of Ina's Collections
*Construction of a Data Lake***

Actual title: IA and Data Management for a Better Curation of Ina's Collection

- Use cases for AI with describing and managing the collections
- 2 million hours for pro use, 17 million hours of legal deposit - how to describe 1 million hours of new (and rebroadcasted) content per year?
 - Also 1.2 million images
 - 15 million videos from 8600 online accounts
 - 624 million tweets

How can AI and Data Management help manage these collections?

- News broadcast - of biggest reuse interest
 - Structural analysis - classifying different program components: anchor, intro, commercial, ... + speech-to-text, aligned with pre-existing metadata
 - Content analysis: OCR on key frames ("discrimination information" => distinguished), face detection & identification

What steps to reach this result?

- Data model to ensure consistency
 - Vocabularies for person names
 - Did analysis of all the data types
 - Model inspired by FRBR/LRM, EN15907, Bibframe, CIDOC-CRM
 - Aimed at breaking down data silos, aim to enable data linking between all different parts of the collection
- Putting data mgmnt and governance practices in place in all departments
 - Different goals and usages of data
 - Tech infra => Data Lake => disconnects data and usage
 - No database is good enough to dit all - combine 4 types of databases to allow all types of usage - Storage module
 - PostgreSQL db
 - Document db in Mongodb
 - Graph db (OpenLink)
 - Search engine: elasticsearch
 - Process module - needs to be synchronized (Talend) - allows quick interaction module for data
 - Abstractions for infra - espousing logical data to business application

- Synchronous REST
- Asynchronous

AI toolbox to analyse documents

- No universal solution
- Focus on business problem: consolidating existing md
- Approx. 50 tools in the toolbox
 - Deep learning image classification to identify different parts of program
 - OCR for retrieving on-screen data
 - Named entity extraction & identification with Wikidata & own vocab

Process & skills to develop

- Not in place yet - not just what tools also what skills & people
- Describe business target & training corpus
- Model building & training
- Needs data specialists

Another use case

- Tools applied to a full day of broadcast

Q&A

- What engines used?
 - OCR: service first then built in-house
 - Classification: important for us
-

**Jon W. Dunn and Bertram Lyons -
AMP: An Audiovisual Metadata Platform to Support Mass Description**

 Slides available at

<https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/7E6YK>

- Indiana U, UoT, NYPL, AVP, Mellon Foundation support

Background and Context

- MDPI!
- Challenge for IU: relatively short period for digitization
- MDPI Internal Content Access content.mdpi.iu.edu
 - Rich metadata for discovery
 - Sometimes all we know is that it's a tape on a shelf
- Challenge
 - Variety of materials
- Opportunity
 - Digitise first
 - How can we use the best automated tools + work with human to achieve our goals.
- Building an open source sw platform to support metadata creation for AV collections (Metadata Generation Mechanism (MGM)) - aim is delivery of metadata to a variety of systems (incl. cloud services, Avalon, ...)
- Existing applications include specific machine learning tools, black-box systems and customized workflows (e.g. MiCO)
- Inputs to AMP Design Process: Group of archivists, computer scientists, information professionals brought to a 3-day workshop

Architecture

- See schema - using postgres database
- Adopted Galaxy workflow system (from bioinformatics community) b/c sharing on campus. Also WGBH also uses Galaxy, we want to share with them
 - Integrates tools you can graphically combine in workflows
- Currently two test cases for AMP pilot development
 - Indiana (University Archives and Cook Music Library) & NYPL's AIDS Activism Videotape collection

Metadata Generation Approaches

- <https://go.iu.edu/amppd>
- Had to select from all the available metadata generators, prioritization made based on
 - Maturity of technology
 - Type of content selected
 - Type of md most useful to managers to extract automatically
- A lot of tools out there. Clear we need to have evaluation criteria.
- Evaluation Criteria
 - Accuracy
 - Input format
 - Output format
 - Growth rate
 - We want this to work at scale
 - Processing time
 - Computing resources
 - Social impact
 - Cost

- Support
- Integration capabilities
- Training

Current Progress

Audio Segmentation

- Tested Ina speech segmenter. Best one.
- Also tested pyannote.
- Uses
 - Anchor points
 - Efficiency. Instead of speech to text 2 hours, can just go straight to the part where's there's speech.
- Common schema. Jjson schema per family.
- ASR.
 - AWS Transcribe 58% accuracy

- Need ground truth. How do we develop them?
- Named Entity Recognition NER
 - Once we created a transcript. Instead of CMS see the transcription. Can run it through NER first. Will get a sense whether it's accurate.
- Video OCR
 - Tools testex
 - (py)tesseract/ffmpeg
 - Google Text Detection
 - How do we do ground truth?
 - Currently working on OpenCV Vision Annotation Tool

Contact:

Silvester Stöger - Coexistence of (Asynchronous) Preservation Processes in Archive Asset Management

Slides available at

<https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/5PWTG>

Archive Asset Management (AAM) more accurate than Media Asset Management. Distinction for Archives.

What are the challenges of an archive in disseminating materials

- Carrier logistics
- Carrier registration
- Carrier
- Preservation of Accompanying materials
- Digitization
 - Do it once, best quality possible
 - Parallelise the throughput
- Quality control
- Content segmentation
 - Policy needed
 - Ontologies needed
- Preservation tasks
 - Storage migration
 - Consistency checks
 - Offsite backhaul
 - Disaster recovery strategy
- Automated MD enrichment and verification
 - But don't forget about the humans. Human Review important.
- Selected provision to cloud

Strategy:

- Understand basic coexisting processes in complex preservation projects
 - Split project in manageable tasks
 - Start with priorities and continue synchronically with other tasks
-

PLENARY SESSION AND OPEN DISCUSSIONS + TECHNICAL AWARDS

- Somaya Langley
 - Quality control
 - Asset management system dictating up stream
 - Ethical discussion
- Kate Murray
 - Open access. Tools and github.
 - Robot taking over, humans survived better learn Python
 - Connect to the linguist community. They have toolsets.
- David Walsh
 - Up until now, Digital tries to capture what's in film. But now digital is moving ahead. More capabilities. You can get so much more out of the original film. You might completely distort it
 - AI. One thing it isn't is intelligence.
 - A lot of data generated on the condition of film, but it doesn't help archivist in any way. There's a bit of film missing, need to prepare for digitisation, no point having so much data. (Really?)
- Somaya: area of activities happening in your own countries. Not sure how to connect. There's a requirement to collaborate beyond FIAF, IASA, JTS,
 - We have to acknowledge all of us on the panel are English speakers and there are some ppl in the room who might find it hard to justify coming here.
 - Some of the Q&A are actually comments. So maybe the format of the talks can accommodate that.
- George: mythical 2025. What then are the roles of the ppl in the room.
 - Kate: There's still work to be done. It will change.
 - Finish digitise. But how to make them more accessible.
 - Somaya: There are a lot of organisations who have not even looked at digitisation. Many don't even have the technical infra or skills to do them.
 - Pushing content into the system. Finding all the errors.
 - Kate: LOC doesn't have a backlog, it has a [can't hear what it is]. Supposed to be a joke but can be real.
 - I don't think it's possible to digitise it once only. Do the best you can. Move on. Don't get so hung up with trying to do everything perfect.
 - David: We go around the world to tell ppl that the time is running up. It's not entirely true. The reality is that it'll get more and more expensive. It's not a cliff face, it's getting steeper and steeper
 - Kate: There's always a choice to be made. Even LOC can't do everything
 - David: When you do succeed in making the case, give money, as we discovered, throwing money at the problem won't solve the problem.
- [?]: as a young AV archivist, other than learning from mentors, I spend a lot of time reading the JTS proceedings. love this symposium, it's bigger than the organisation

contributing to it. All brought together. Greater and bigger than sum of its parts. Exciting that it's still going on. Even though we might all be doing something else in the future.

- [Casey, WGBH]: Climate change. We need to think about this as a community. Just want to put that out there.
- Somaya: storage cost.
- David: Might be worse than this. We might want to plan beyond current structures powering up data stores. Pick out two and three items, put in B&W polyester films, stick it in a cave.
- Erwin: On climate change. every digital preservation conference, it's not about technology, it's about people. It's about how we convince ppl that it's important. It's about processes. What are the spaces we need to create for discussion about climate change really happen.
- [? Lady]: I want to take part in the symposium. But presentation ends on the dot, no time to ask questions.
 - Press statement at the end of the conference. Joint statement of what we want.
 - Somaya: So many ppl in the room. We should work together.
- Ross: There should be a metric on how much energy we use, on top of what we have now.
- Somaya: IASA TC06 for born digital video. We need to generate information in a different way, in a more agile way. If anyone knows someone who knows someone, please contact us.
- Kate: What folks would imagine, want JTS to be, in 3 years time? More interactivity? Great thing is it brings folks all around the world together. If you were to do it in 3 years time. What would you like to see for your next JTS?
 - [Half the room raised their hands wanted it to be more interactive]
 - James Lindner: break out room. Put ppl around the table. Technical topic discussions. This is the core strength of JTS.
 - Giorgio: I don't have any other expertise. My expertise is develop optical system for film scanners. The only place I feel out of place.
 - James Lindner: List interest area.
 - Tre: AMIA has breakout session for more specific topics. How to navigate career audiovisual archivist.
 - Andrea Kalas: Follow film, video, audio, and TV. Converges. What are the things that's similar? What are the differences we need to know?
 - George Blood: I come to JTS to not be the nerdiest person in the room. But some might not be like me. Some come to learn. Maybe first time attendee programme. AMIA randomly pair them up. Or ARS, more deliberate pairing. Reach out deeply to ppl who are coming here to learn.
 - Somaya: I've been working in the gig economy. Many in the room are too. I would want to take as many mentors as I can get. So yes.
 - Casey: posting slides on Google drive is very helpful. Some don't have notes.
 - Erwin: we recorded about 75% of sessions. We will process and upload online
- David: Am I the only one who feel that all these digital preservation systems are overly complicated?
 - Erwin: There's doing the technical things and there's managing things.

- [sitting next to George]: back then, when we developed EAD. Soon we have archivist toolkit and then archive space. More ppl have access to it. Speech to text still in the development. Eventually it'll evolve. 90% won't be using it.
 - BTW Python is great.
- Raymond: I've seen this before. Underlying principles are the same. Back then, I spend time around studios, they're going through the same thing. Trying to tackle digital. They have conferences like this too.
 - There's a new paper out by 5 major studios about what's next? Archiving is in the plan. We have to care about archiving. You've done something right that they included in the 10 years plan.
- Andrea Kalas, paramount: harder to drive advocacy for digital. Doesn't have the same effect as film.
- Somaya: we do have to share our fields
- James Lindner: Analogue, very squirrely. A lot of them have gone away.
 - Working with young ppl, born-digital native, is fantastic, they just get it.
 - Things have gotten much better.
 - The steep end of preservation is always access.
 - It'll always hard to get money for preservation.
 - We do preservation for access.
 - I've seen it in many archives, they're successful.
- [lady] : Future? What do we want to share? What are we leaving behind?
 - Reto: For future, live streaming of the symposium would be great.

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